

SDG indicators for Assessing the Sustainability Impacts of Agricultural Trade

MATS Deliverable 2.1

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Summary

The MATS project aims to explore the links between agricultural trade, markets, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being. Work Package (WP) 2 is to provide an enhanced analytical framework including theoretical foundations and methodological guidance for all subsequent analyses. Task 2.1 feeds into this broader analytical framework by identifying SDG indicators - from the total set of 248 - that could inform the design and operationalisation of the analytical framework.

To this end, a selection process has been carried out starting with the 248 indicators that represent the official list of indicators for the SDGs to a final selection of 56 indicators considered most relevant to the scope of MATS. In selecting the indicators, the following were considered: the contribution to assessing the linkages between agricultural trade, sustainability, investment, and human welfare; the formulation at a geographical scale appropriate for MATS purposes; possible overlap with other indicators; the potential usefulness for the 15 case studies.

To structure the list of indicators, we use a conceptual framework that places them around six categories related to agri-food value chains, providing, in turn, a more comprehensive and systemic view of agri-food trade. The conceptual framework was informed by the results of WP1 and provides a common basis for the analyses to be carried out in WP3.

The resulting list of 56 indicators is now under consultation with project partners to assess actual applicability, along with gathering ideas on how to keep advancing the development of the analytical framework for MATS.

First indications from these consultations are that most SDG indicators are impact-indicators and insufficient as such in assessing more systemically the linkages between agri-food trade and sustainability. At a more practical level, we found that the initial case study plans are mainly focused on addressing the social, economic, and environmental impacts of agri-food trade, and need to become much stronger related to policy and governance, knowledge exchange and innovations, and human capital.

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Introduction

Background and purpose of the deliverable

MATS explores in-depth the links between agricultural trade, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being. It aims at identifying key leverage points that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on sustainability and human well-being. Work Package (WP) 2 aims to provide an enhanced analytical framework that guides all analyses while acknowledging the diversity of perspectives and narratives that underlie debates around agri-food trade. This analytical framework provides theoretical foundations and methodological guidance – including SDG indicators, methods, and tools.

This deliverable D2.1 should be seen as a first steppingstone towards the enhanced analytical framework that will be the last deliverable of WP2 (D2.4). D2.1 is to contribute to review the indicators that accompany the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), select the ones that seem most suitable for subsequent analyses, and, if needed, identify additional indicators.

D2.1 is composed of

- This report with information on the methodology applied and a discussion of results.
- The annexes where all the results regarding indicators are detailed.
- An Excel file with an interactive system to explore results and indicators in a more accessible way. The excel file will be the public version of the deliverable.

The deliverable is based on consultations with WP2 partners.

Methodology

Selection process

FIGURE 1.
SELECTION PROCESS DIAGRAMS

The SDGs encompass 17 goals with 248 SDG indicators¹, that were established to help measure and assess progress towards achieving sustainable development. For this deliverable, a selection of the most relevant SDG indicators in the agricultural trade and production context has been carried out.

Considering direct, indirect, and induced impacts, all SDGs are relevant to assess trade-related impacts on sustainable development. However, to facilitate an efficient selection process of analysis, the most relevant indicators for a sustainable trade analysis were pre-selected:

- SDGs referred to in the call and project scope (1, 2, 3, 6, 13 and 15) and the related indicators;

¹ As contained in the Annex of the resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 6 July 2017, Work of the Statistical Commission pertaining to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (A/RES/71/313), annual refinements contained in E/CN.3/2018/2 (Annex II), E/CN.3/2019/2 (Annex II), 2020 Comprehensive Review changes (Annex II) and annual refinements (Annex III) contained in E/CN.3/2020/2, and annual refinements contained in E/CN.3/2021/2 (Annex). Please note that the total number of indicators listed in the global indicator framework of SDG indicators is 247, but the data base pretend to include 248, although one indicator is under development.

- other SDGs targeted in the case studies (5, 7, 8, 10 and 12) and the related indicators;
- indicators belonging to the [SDG Trade Monitor](#) (10, 11, 12 and 17).

After applying the aforementioned 3 parameters, the selected number of SDG indicators got down to 172. (**Figure 1**).

Thereafter, three additional criteria were applied for the final selection of SDG indicators: the geographical scope of the indicator (**C1**), the measured item (**C2**), and the scope and needs of the case studies (**C3**).

(C1) The national focused SDG indicators and the global focused SDG indicators have been eliminated from the selection process, as they are of limited utility for our purpose: both global and national indicators are less suitable for comparisons between case studies, which mostly have a sub-national, sector or value-chain scope. Also, Exploring systemic effects of agricultural trade at the subnational level, which most of the spillover effects can be better mapped and identified.

Example for (C1)

13.1.2 Number of countries that adopt and implement national disaster risk reduction strategies in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030

1.2.2 Proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions

(C2) Subsequently, the remaining SDG indicators were analysed considering what they are aiming to measure. Those that measure aspects directly related to trade and within the scope of MATS were selected. For further guidance, the trade and sustainability categories that defined the focus of the analysis at the proposal stage were used:

- **Consumption:** food security intended as availability to a sufficient amount of food, access to adequate resources to obtain food, utilization of food through adequate diet and safe water, and stability of supply and access (FAO, 2006).
- **Production inputs:** natural inputs like land and soil fertility, water, vegetation cover and habitat; production inputs, research and development, machinery and equipment, finance.

- **Production outputs and outcomes:** employment and income, products to be sold, revenue and externalities on air, soil, water, biodiversity, human health, etc.
- **Political economy:** policy, governance and regulatory frameworks favoring or hindering conditions for sustainable development.

Example for (C2)

3.5.2 Alcohol per capita consumption (aged 15 years and older) within a calendar year in litres of pure alcohol

10.6.1 Proportion of members and voting rights of developing countries in international organizations

(C3) Based on a review of the initial case study plans, related SDG indicators were identified, and compared with the existing list to ensure good coverage of case study needs, purposes, and contextual specificities. The SDG indicators that could not be associated with any case study were eliminated from the list, under the assumption that case studies provide a sufficient overview of trade contexts and regimes.

Example for (C3)

2.5.1 Number of (a) plant and (b) animal genetic resources for food and agriculture secured in either medium- or long-term conservation facilities

2.5.2 Proportion of local breeds classified as being at risk of extinction

The full list of SDG indicators eliminated under these criteria can be found in the Table "Results - Not selected SDG indicators" (See Annex 1).

At the end, 56 SDG indicators have been selected. The complete list of SDG indicators can be found in the tab "Results – Selected SDG indicators" (See Annex 2).

Classification

To facilitate a better overview, the indicator list has been structured using several categories of agri-food systems. This places the list of indicators within a more comprehensive and systemic view of agri-food trade that

acknowledges the linkages with sustainability and human well-being, as well as investments (instead of thinking of trade as an isolated activity).

Figure 2 shows agri-food trade as a key part of the agri-food system – comprising the value chain activities and multidimensional contexts. The context affects value chain activities, including trade (Drivers), which in turn change the context, drive food systems change and impact the sustainability of the system and human well-being (Impacts).

The six categories help explain the broad linkages between agri-food trade, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being. This is also reflected in the initial mapping of linkages in WP1 (see D1.1). The basic concept is enriched with insights from the four capitals framework (Ekins, Dresner, & Dahlström, 2008), which has been used in food systems frameworks such as TEEB AgriFood (TEEB, 2018), AFSSA framework (Hubeau et al., 2017) and the Climate change, food security, and livelihoods framework (Connolly-Boutin & Smit, 2016).

FIGURE 2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR CLASSIFYING SDG INDICATORS

Organizing the SDG indicators in categories that reflect the aim of assessing the linkages between agri-food trade, sustainability, investments and human well-being will give us a more systemic understanding of what it means to select or prioritize certain SDG indicators over others. Furthermore, it will provide a coherent framework for implementing all subsequent analyses, and for integrating the results and findings across case studies and model-based analyses.

Prioritization through consultation process

Considering that the purpose of the 56 indicators selected from the SDGs is to inform the design of the framework for all further analyses, it is essential to assess the selected indicators for their interconnectivity between WPs, as well as the needs of the 15 case studies as pilots for further use of the analytical framework for systemic assessment of agricultural trade that MATS will propose.

To implement this assessment, we started a process of consultation with MATS partners, case study leaders and case study partners and in this way, with experts and practitioners in agri-food trade.

The final objective of the consultation process is

1. to assess the broader relevance of the SDG indicators in exploring issues at the interphase of food systems, trade, and sustainability;
2. to ensure the relevance for specific case studies;
3. to obtain further suggestions for the analytical framework development.

The consultation is conducted through an online survey² where respondents select the most suitable SDG indicators for each category of the conceptual framework (Figure 2), based on a) their relevance (the indicator should help to analyse and measure an important aspect of trade - sustainability relations) and b) their quality (specific, achievable, replicable, time-bound).

² The survey is included in Annex 2.

The results of the consultation will provide us with a prioritized list of indicators by each category and a general understanding of the usefulness of SDG indicators for the purposes of MATS.

On a more practical level, the case study leaders will have the chance to share their opinion on the relevance of the SDG indicators, specifically selected for their case study³. The specific list for each CS was made by analysing the preliminary information provided by each case study at MATS proposal stage. The feedback from case study leaders will give us a general understanding of the purposes and needs of each case study analysis, and it will also contribute to obtaining a common understanding of the focus, purpose, and expected outcomes of the case study analysis.

The online survey has been sent to MATS partners, their institutions colleagues and case study leaders, including 54 agents. The request has been sent the 21 March 2022, and the deadline for responses is 31 March 2022.

Results

Set of SDG indicators

The list of 56 selected SDG indicators is presented in the tab "Results - selected SDG indicators" of the Excel file. To each indicator a category has been assigned, and this allows us to analyse how well the defined categories are represented within SDGs indicators (Figure 3)

³ The specific SDG indicators selected for each case study are included in Annex 3.

FIGURE 3. COVERAGE OF SDG INDICATORS BY CATEGORY

As shown in **Figure 3**, the distribution of SDG indicators covers quite well all the established categories, although there is a little difference with respect to the Economy & Market and Environmental/Natural Capital category. The SDG indicators are mainly impact indicators related to environmental, economic, and social dimensions, but there are few indicators related to processes and flows within the agri-food value chain.

The fact that Economy and Market is the category with more associated SDG indicators responds to its more direct relation with trade topic, which is the focus of MATS. The fact that some categories are represented by a greater number of indicators is much a reflection of data and measurability (e.g., Social Capital vs. Economy & Market).

Figure 4 shows that the SDGs listed at the MATS proposal stage are entirely represented by the final list of SDG indicators.

FIGURE 4. SELECTED SDG INDICATORS SUBDIVIDED BY CATEGORY

The SDGs referred to in the MATS proposal were used as the basis for pre-selecting indicators. At a second stage, we reviewed the indicators by decoupling them from the SDGs to exclude those not associated with the agri-food value chains or that do not address its linkages with sustainability or human well-being and investments **(C2)**.

Prioritization

To be developed when results from the consultation process are available. This deliverable will be updated once results from this process are available, analyzed, and synthesized.

Case study related SDG indicators

The third selection criteria **(C3)** relate to the indicators that were already suggested for each case study during proposal development. The initial information provided by CS included the planned SDGs to be address, but for this analysis they have not been considered. That because, when consider SDGs at indicator’s level, the usefulness may not coincide.

Based on this initial plan, we could check how the case studies cover the different categories. **Figure 5** presents the results of this analysis.

FIGURE 5. CASE STUDIES ANALYSIS COVERAGE BY CATEGORIES

The planned analysis of relationships between agri-food trade and sustainability through the case studies seems to be focused on social, environmental, and economic categories. This could be influenced by the fact that data in these categories are more readily available compared to others like governance or knowledge. Based on this it seems necessary to reflect on expanding the focus in the case studies as planned initially and to try and deliver a more systemic understanding of agri-food systems and trade. Institutional frameworks and governance arrangements will play a central role when trade regimes and practices are assessed, and we need to ensure that the information that is required for this assessment is being gathered.

Important to note that the information used in this analysis is preliminary; therefore, these results need to be complemented when updated case study plannings and the results from the consultation process are available.

Linkages with others WP

T1.1 - The initial mapping of linkages between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being have been used in this deliverable as an input for classified indicators in the six categories.

T2.4 - These results are the first steppingstone towards the enhanced analytical framework that will be the final output of T2.4.

T3.1 - The comparative analysis of the indicators suggested in initial case study plans is a first step towards a more comprehensive planning of the 15 case studies. This will then inform the elaboration of guidance documents and of a common reporting template, as a final output of T3.1.

T3.3 - The prioritised list of SDG indicators expects to be an initial step for the final Integrated model-based simulation and assessment of linkages with agricultural market, trade, and investment dynamics in T3.3.

Conclusion

The set of indicators presented in this report and the related Excel file is to support the identification of key leverage points that foster positive and reduce negative impacts of agricultural trade on sustainability and human well-being. When selecting indicators, we aimed at providing a more systemic view of agri-food trade, avoiding assessing it as an isolated activity.

The SDG indicators are meaningful in orienting the analytical framework. However, they are not sufficient in themselves for assessing the relations between sustainability and trade. This is because the UN SDG indicators are mainly impact indicators that have not been designed with an organizational (value chain) focus or for use in more complex concepts with a systemic perspective.

The final list of indicators that will eventually be part of the analytical framework will therefore not be restricted to SDG indicators but will use them as input.

From a very initial analysis of the information provided by case study leaders, it seems that the selected indicators of the SDGs cover the different contexts planned for the in-depth analysis. As the initial case study plans mostly focus on social, environmental, and economic aspects, it needs to be ensured that the case studies also address aspects related to policy, institutional frameworks and governance arrangements, knowledge and technologies, human capital, interactions and agency.

The ongoing consultation process is to assess the actual applicability of SDG indicators, along with obtaining ideas on how to further advance the development of the analytical framework for MATS.

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Annex 1: Results - Not selected SDG indicators

C1-National and Global indicators

1.2.1 Proportion of population living below the national poverty line, by sex and age

1.2.2 Proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions

1.5.3 Number of countries that adopt and implement national disaster risk reduction strategies in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030

10.7.2 Number of countries with migration policies that facilitate orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people

11.a.1 Number of countries that have national urban policies or regional development plans that (a) respond to population dynamics; (b) ensure balanced territorial development; and (c) increase local fiscal space

11.b.1 Number of countries that adopt and implement national disaster risk reduction strategies in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030

12.1.1 Number of countries developing, adopting or implementing policy instruments aimed at supporting the shift to sustainable consumption and production

13.1.2 Number of countries that adopt and implement national disaster risk reduction strategies in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030

13.2.1 Number of countries with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

13.b.1 Number of least developed countries and small island developing States with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

15.6.1 Number of countries that have adopted legislative, administrative and policy frameworks to ensure fair and equitable sharing of benefits

15.8.1 Proportion of countries adopting relevant national legislation and adequately resourcing the prevention or control of invasive alien species

15.9.1 (a) Number of countries that have established national targets in accordance with or similar to Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 in their national biodiversity strategy and action plans and the progress reported towards these targets; and (b) integration of biodiversity into national accounting and reporting systems, defined as implementation of the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting

17.10.1 Worldwide weighted tariff-average

5.6.2 Number of countries with laws and regulations that guarantee full and equal access to women and men aged 15 years and older to sexual and reproductive health care, information and education

5.a.2 Proportion of countries where the legal framework (including customary law) guarantees women's equal rights to land ownership and/or control

C2-Elements of Evaluation

1.5.1 Number of deaths, missing persons and directly affected persons attributed to disasters per 100,000 population

1.5.2 Direct economic loss attributed to disasters in relation to global gross domestic product (GDP)

1.5.4 Proportion of local governments that adopt and implement local disaster risk reduction strategies in line with national disaster risk reduction strategies

10.3.1 Proportion of population reporting having personally felt discriminated against or harassed in the previous 12 months on the basis of a ground of discrimination prohibited under international human rights law

10.4.1 Labour share of GDP

10.4.2 Redistributive impact of fiscal policy⁴

10.5.1 Financial Soundness Indicators

10.6.1 Proportion of members and voting rights of developing countries in international organizations

10.7.1 Recruitment cost borne by employee as a proportion of monthly income earned in country of destination

10.7.3 Number of people who died or disappeared in the process of migration towards an international destination

10.7.4 Proportion of the population who are refugees, by country of origin

10.c.1 Remittance costs as a proportion of the amount remitted

11.1.1 Proportion of urban population living in slums, informal settlements or inadequate housing

11.2.1 Proportion of population that has convenient access to public transport, by sex, age and persons with disabilities

11.3.2 Proportion of cities with a direct participation structure of civil society in urban planning and management that operate regularly and democratically

11.5.1 Number of deaths, missing persons and directly affected persons attributed to disasters per 100,000 population

11.5.2 Direct economic loss in relation to global GDP, damage to critical infrastructure and number of disruptions to basic services, attributed to disasters

11.6.1 Proportion of municipal solid waste collected and managed in controlled facilities out of total municipal waste generated, by cities

11.6.2 Annual mean levels of fine particulate matter (e.g. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) in cities (population weighted)

11.7.1 Average share of the built-up area of cities that is open space for public use for all, by sex, age and persons with disabilities

11.7.2 Proportion of persons victim of physical or sexual harassment, by sex, age, disability status and place of occurrence, in the previous 12 months

11.b.2 Proportion of local governments that adopt and implement local disaster risk reduction strategies in line with national disaster risk reduction strategies

12.4.1 Number of parties to international multilateral environmental agreements on hazardous waste, and other chemicals that meet their commitments and obligations in transmitting information as required by each relevant agreement

12.4.2 (a) Hazardous waste generated per capita; and (b) proportion of hazardous waste treated, by type of treatment

12.5.1 National recycling rate, tons of material recycled

12.6.1 Number of companies publishing sustainability reports

12.8.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment

12.a.1 Installed renewable energy-generating capacity in developing countries (in watts per capita)

12.b.1 Implementation of standard accounting tools to monitor the economic and environmental aspects of tourism sustainability

13.1.1 Number of deaths, missing persons and directly affected persons attributed to disasters per 100,000 population

13.1.3 Proportion of local governments that adopt and implement local disaster risk reduction strategies in line with national disaster risk reduction strategies

13.a.1 Amounts provided and mobilized in United States dollars per year in relation to the continued existing collective mobilization goal of the \$100 billion commitment through to 2025

14.7.1 Sustainable fisheries as a proportion of GDP in small island developing States, least developed countries and all countries

15.7.1 Proportion of traded wildlife that was poached or illicitly trafficked

15.b.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments

15.c.1 Proportion of traded wildlife that was poached or illicitly trafficked

17.3.1 Foreign direct investment, official development assistance and South-South cooperation as a proportion of gross national income

2.2.1 Prevalence of stunting (height for age <-2 standard deviation from the median of the World Health Organization (WHO) Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age

2.2.3 Prevalence of anaemia in women aged 15 to 49 years, by pregnancy status (percentage)

3.1.1 Maternal mortality ratio

3.1.2 Proportion of births attended by skilled health personnel

3.2.1 Under-5 mortality rate

3.2.2 Neonatal mortality rate

3.3.1 Number of new HIV infections per 1,000 uninfected population, by sex, age and key populations

- 3.3.2 Tuberculosis incidence per 100,000 population
- 3.3.3 Malaria incidence per 1,000 population
- 3.3.4 Hepatitis B incidence per 100,000 population
- 3.3.5 Number of people requiring interventions against neglected tropical diseases
- 3.4.1 Mortality rate attributed to cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes or chronic respiratory disease
- 3.4.2 Suicide mortality rate
- 3.5.1 Coverage of treatment interventions (pharmacological, psychosocial and rehabilitation and aftercare services) for substance use disorders
- 3.5.2 Alcohol per capita consumption (aged 15 years and older) within a calendar year in litres of pure alcohol
- 3.6.1 Death rate due to road traffic injuries
- 3.7.1 Proportion of women of reproductive age (aged 15–49 years) who have their need for family planning satisfied with modern methods
- 3.7.2 Adolescent birth rate (aged 10–14 years; aged 15–19 years) per 1,000 women in that age group
- 3.8.2 Proportion of population with large household expenditures on health as a share of total household expenditure or income
- 3.9.3 Mortality rate attributed to unintentional poisoning
- 3.a.1 Age-standardized prevalence of current tobacco use among persons aged 15 years and older
- 3.b.1 Proportion of the target population covered by all vaccines included in their national programme
- 3.b.2 Total net official development assistance to medical research and basic health sectors
- 3.b.3 Proportion of health facilities that have a core set of relevant essential medicines available and affordable on a sustainable basis
- 3.c.1 Health worker density and distribution
- 3.d.1 International Health Regulations (IHR) capacity and health emergency preparedness
- 3.d.2 Percentage of bloodstream infections due to selected antimicrobial-resistant organisms
- 5.2.1 Proportion of ever-partnered women and girls aged 15 years and older subjected to physical, sexual or psychological violence by a current or former intimate partner in the previous 12 months, by form of violence and by age
- 5.2.2 Proportion of women and girls aged 15 years and older subjected to sexual violence by persons other than an intimate partner in the previous 12 months, by age and place of occurrence
- 5.3.1 Proportion of women aged 20–24 years who were married or in a union before age 15 and before age 18
- 5.3.2 Proportion of girls and women aged 15–49 years who have undergone female genital mutilation/cutting, by age
- 5.4.1 Proportion of time spent on unpaid domestic and care work, by sex, age and location
- 5.5.1 Proportion of seats held by women in (a) national parliaments and (b) local governments
- 5.5.2 Proportion of women in managerial positions

- 5.6.1 Proportion of women aged 15–49 years who make their own informed decisions regarding sexual relations, contraceptive use and reproductive health care
- 5.b.1 Proportion of individuals who own a mobile telephone, by sex
- 5.c.1 Proportion of countries with systems to track and make public allocations for gender equality and women’s empowerment
- 6.1.1 Proportion of population using safely managed drinking water services
- 6.2.1 Proportion of population using (a) safely managed sanitation services and (b) a hand-washing facility with soap and water
- 6.3.1 Proportion of domestic and industrial wastewater flows safely treated
- 6.5.2 Proportion of transboundary basin area with an operational arrangement for water cooperation
- 6.a.1 Amount of water- and sanitation-related official development assistance that is part of a government-coordinated spending plan
- 6.b.1 Proportion of local administrative units with established and operational policies and procedures for participation of local communities in water and sanitation management
- 7.1.1 Proportion of population with access to electricity
- 7.1.2 Proportion of population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology
- 7.3.1 Energy intensity measured in terms of primary energy and GDP
- 7.a.1 International financial flows to developing countries in support of clean energy research and development and renewable energy production, including in hybrid systems
- 8.10.1 (a) Number of commercial bank branches per 100,000 adults and (b) number of automated teller machines (ATMs) per 100,000 adults
- 8.10.2 Proportion of adults (15 years and older) with an account at a bank or other financial institution or with a mobile-money-service provider
- 8.6.1 Proportion of youth (aged 15–24 years) not in education, employment or training
- 8.7.1 Proportion and number of children aged 5–17 years engaged in child labour, by sex and age
- 8.8.1 Fatal and non-fatal occupational injuries per 100,000 workers, by sex and migrant status
- 8.9.1 Tourism direct GDP as a proportion of total GDP and in growth rate
- 8.b.1 Existence of a developed and operationalized national strategy for youth employment, as a distinct strategy or as part of a national employment strategy

(C3) Case study comparison

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- 13.3.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment
 - 15.5.1 Red List Index

2.5.1 Number of (a) plant and (b) animal genetic resources for food and agriculture secured in either medium- or long-term conservation facilities

2.5.2 Proportion of local breeds classified as being at risk of extinction

Duplicate

1.4.2 Proportion of total adult population with secure tenure rights to land, (a) with legally recognized documentation, and (b) who perceive their rights to land as secure, by sex and type of tenure

12.2.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP

12.2.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

7.b.1 Installed renewable energy-generating capacity in developing countries (in watts per capita)

No suitable replacement indicator was proposed. The global statistical community is encouraged to work to develop an indicator that could be proposed for the 2025 comprehensive review. See E/CN.3/2020/2, paragraph 23.

Not related with the proposal

14.1.1 (a) Index of coastal eutrophication; and (b) plastic debris density

14.2.1 Number of countries using ecosystem-based approaches to managing marine areas

14.3.1 Average marine acidity (pH) measured at agreed suite of representative sampling stations

14.4.1 Proportion of fish stocks within biologically sustainable levels

14.5.1 Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas

14.6.1 Degree of implementation of international instruments aiming to combat illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing

14.a.1 Proportion of total research budget allocated to research in the field of marine technology

14.b.1 Degree of application of a legal/regulatory/ policy/institutional framework which recognizes and protects access rights for small-scale fisheries

14.c.1 Number of countries making progress in ratifying, accepting and implementing through legal, policy and institutional frameworks, ocean-related instruments that implement international law, as reflected in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, for the conservation and sustainable use of the oceans and their resources

16.1.1 Number of victims of intentional homicide per 100,000 population, by sex and age

16.1.2 Conflict-related deaths per 100,000 population, by sex, age and cause

16.1.3 Proportion of population subjected to (a) physical violence, (b) psychological violence and (c) sexual violence in the previous 12 months

16.1.4 Proportion of population that feel safe walking alone around the area they live

16.10.1 Number of verified cases of killing, kidnapping, enforced disappearance, arbitrary detention and torture of journalists, associated media personnel, trade unionists and human rights advocates in the previous 12 months

- 16.10.2 Number of countries that adopt and implement constitutional, statutory and/or policy guarantees for public access to information
- 16.2.1 Proportion of children aged 1–17 years who experienced any physical punishment and/or psychological aggression by caregivers in the past month
- 16.2.2 Number of victims of human trafficking per 100,000 population, by sex, age and form of exploitation
- 16.2.3 Proportion of young women and men aged 18–29 years who experienced sexual violence by age 18
- 16.3.1 Proportion of victims of violence in the previous 12 months who reported their victimization to competent authorities or other officially recognized conflict resolution mechanisms
- 16.3.2 Unsentenced detainees as a proportion of overall prison population
- 16.3.3 Proportion of the population who have experienced a dispute in the past two years and who accessed a formal or informal dispute resolution mechanism, by type of mechanism
- 16.4.1 Total value of inward and outward illicit financial flows (in current United States dollars)
- 16.4.2 Proportion of seized, found or surrendered arms whose illicit origin or context has been traced or established by a competent authority in line with international instruments
- 16.5.1 Proportion of persons who had at least one contact with a public official and who paid a bribe to a public official, or were asked for a bribe by those public officials, during the previous 12 months
- 16.5.2 Proportion of businesses that had at least one contact with a public official and that paid a bribe to a public official, or were asked for a bribe by those public officials during the previous 12 months
- 16.6.1 Primary government expenditures as a proportion of original approved budget, by sector (or by budget codes or similar)
- 16.6.2 Proportion of population satisfied with their last experience of public services
- 16.7.1 Proportions of positions in national and local institutions, including (a) the legislatures; (b) the public service; and (c) the judiciary, compared to national distributions, by sex, age, persons with disabilities and population groups
- 16.7.2 Proportion of population who believe decision-making is inclusive and responsive, by sex, age, disability and population group
- 16.8.1 Proportion of members and voting rights of developing countries in international organizations
- 16.9.1 Proportion of children under 5 years of age whose births have been registered with a civil authority, by age
- 16.a.1 Existence of independent national human rights institutions in compliance with the Paris Principles
- 16.b.1 Proportion of population reporting having personally felt discriminated against or harassed in the previous 12 months on the basis of a ground of discrimination prohibited under international human rights law
- 17.1.1 Total government revenue as a proportion of GDP, by source
- 17.1.2 Proportion of domestic budget funded by domestic taxes

- 17.13.1 Macroeconomic Dashboard
- 17.14.1 Number of countries with mechanisms in place to enhance policy coherence of sustainable development
- 17.15.1 Extent of use of country-owned results frameworks and planning tools by providers of development cooperation
- 17.16.1 Number of countries reporting progress in multi-stakeholder development effectiveness monitoring frameworks that support the achievement of the sustainable development goals
- 17.17.1 Amount in United States dollars committed to public-private partnerships for infrastructure
- 17.18.1 Statistical capacity indicator for Sustainable Development Goal monitoring
- 17.18.2 Number of countries that have national statistical legislation that complies with the Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics
- 17.18.3 Number of countries with a national statistical plan that is fully funded and under implementation, by source of funding
- 17.19.1 Dollar value of all resources made available to strengthen statistical capacity in developing countries
- 17.19.2 Proportion of countries that (a) have conducted at least one population and housing census in the last 10 years; and (b) have achieved 100 per cent birth registration and 80 per cent death registration
- 17.2.1 Net official development assistance, total and to least developed countries, as a proportion of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Development Assistance Committee donors' gross national income (GNI)
- 17.3.2 Volume of remittances (in United States dollars) as a proportion of total GDP
- 17.4.1 Debt service as a proportion of exports of goods and services
- 17.5.1 Number of countries that adopt and implement investment promotion regimes for developing countries, including the least developed countries
- 17.6.1 Fixed Internet broadband subscriptions per 100 inhabitants, by speed⁵
- 17.8.1 Proportion of individuals using the Internet
- 17.9.1 Dollar value of financial and technical assistance (including through North-South, South-South and triangular cooperation) committed to developing countries
- 4.1.1 Proportion of children and young people (a) in grades 2/3; (b) at the end of primary; and (c) at the end of lower secondary achieving at least a minimum proficiency level in (i) reading and (ii) mathematics, by sex
- 4.1.2 Completion rate (primary education, lower secondary education, upper secondary education)
- 4.2.1 Proportion of children aged 24–59 months who are developmentally on track in health, learning and psychosocial well-being, by sex
- 4.2.2 Participation rate in organized learning (one year before the official primary entry age), by sex
- 4.3.1 Participation rate of youth and adults in formal and non-formal education and training in the previous 12 months, by sex
- 4.4.1 Proportion of youth and adults with information and communications technology (ICT) skills, by type of skill

4.5.1 Parity indices (female/male, rural/urban, bottom/top wealth quintile and others such as disability status, indigenous peoples and conflict-affected, as data become available) for all education indicators on this list that can be disaggregated

4.6.1 Proportion of population in a given age group achieving at least a fixed level of proficiency in functional (a) literacy and (b) numeracy skills, by sex

4.7.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment

4.a.1 Proportion of schools offering basic services, by type of service

4.b.1 Volume of official development assistance flows for scholarships by sector and type of study

4.c.1 Proportion of teachers with the minimum required qualifications, by education level

9.1.1 Proportion of the rural population who live within 2 km of an all-season road

9.1.2 Passenger and freight volumes, by mode of transport

9.2.1 Manufacturing value added as a proportion of GDP and per capita

9.2.2 Manufacturing employment as a proportion of total employment

9.3.1 Proportion of small-scale industries in total industry value added

9.3.2 Proportion of small-scale industries with a loan or line of credit

9.4.1 CO2 emission per unit of value added

9.5.1 Research and development expenditure as a proportion of GDP

9.5.2 Researchers (in full-time equivalent) per million inhabitants

9.a.1 Total official international support (official development assistance plus other official flows) to infrastructure

9.b.1 Proportion of medium and high-tech industry value added in total value added

9.c.1 Proportion of population covered by a mobile network, by technology

Annex 2: Results – Selected SDG indicators

Economy & Markets

- 1.a.1 Total official development assistance grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the recipient country's gross national income
- 10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
- 12.c.1 Amount of fossil-fuel subsidies (production and consumption) per unit of GDP
- 17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports
- 17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
- 2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
- 2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
- 2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
- 2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies
- 8.1.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita
- 8.2.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person
- 8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

Environment/Natural Capital

- 11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
- 12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index
- 13.2.2 Total greenhouse gas emissions per year
- 15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area
- 15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
- 15.4.2 Mountain Green Cover Index
- 6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality
- 6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources

7.2.1 Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption

8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP

8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Human Capital

1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)

1.4.1 Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services

10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities

2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment

2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)

2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height $>+2$ or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)

3.8.1 Coverage of essential health services

3.9.1 Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution

3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities

10.b.1 Total resource flows for development, by recipient and donor countries and type of flow (e.g. official development assistance, foreign direct investment and other flows)

15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management

15.a.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments

17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies

2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture

6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time

6.5.1 Degree of integrated water resources management

6.6.1 Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time

Social Capital

1.3.1 Proportion of population covered by social protection floors/systems, by sex, distinguishing children, unemployed persons, older persons, persons with disabilities, pregnant women, newborns, work-injury victims and the poor and the vulnerable

10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population

2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status

5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex

5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure

8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex

8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities

8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities

8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

Policy, Governance & Regulation

1.a.2 Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)

1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending

11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)

12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation

15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type

15.4.1 Coverage by protected areas of important sites for mountain biodiversity

2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

Annex 3: Questionnaire

Introduction

MATS focuses on exploring the links between agricultural trade, markets, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being.

Work Package (WP) 2 aims to provide an enhanced analytical framework to guide the implementation of all subsequent analyses while acknowledging the diversity of perspectives and narratives that underlie debates around agri-food trade. The analytical framework provides theoretical foundations and methodological guidance, including indicators, methods, and tools.

Within WP2, Task 2.1 feeds into this broader analytical framework by deriving relevant indicators from the total set of 248 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) indicators. Note that the list of indicators that will eventually be part of the analytical framework will not be restricted to the selected SDGs indicators but use them as an input. This consultation process is to assess the actual applicability of SDG indicators, along with crowdsourcing ideas on how to keep advancing the development of the analytical framework for MATS.

This work is in this sense a steppingstone for the last deliverable of WP2. It is also based on results from WP1 in identifying the six dimensions around which the indicators are clustered.

Methodology

To obtain the final list of indicators for MATS, a selection process has been carried out. Of the 248 indicators that exist in the official list of indicators for the SDGs, only the indicators relevant to the scope of MATS project have been considered. Several criteria have been applied to select relevant indicators:

- Indicators need to contribute to the assessment of the linkages between agri-food trade, sustainability, and human well-being.
- The geographical scope of the indicators
- Minimising redundancies between indicator coverage

- Indicators need to be of relevance and considered necessary for the set of 15 case studies.

The result is a list of 56 indicators that is now considered in a consultation with all partners.

To make structure the list of indicators, we use a conceptual framework that organizes them around clusters of concepts (Figure 1).

FIGURE 6. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR CLASSIFYING TRADE AND SUSTAINABLE RELATED INDICATORS.

Your feedback and suggestions needed

As this indicator list is to be part of a comprehensive and more generally applicable analytical framework to assess the relationship between trade and sustainability, we would like to ensure its **relevance and quality** for this purpose. In this respect, we would like to open a first consultation process with you as experts and practitioners on agri-food trade to obtain a deeper view on indicators and be able to prioritise those most suitable for MATS.

For that, we elaborated this questionnaire structured in three main sections:

- A. General information: to know your relationship with the project, your field of work, affiliations, and personal contact information to engage you if necessary.
- B. General assessment of indicators: to go deeper into the quality and relevance of the indicators selected for MATS.
- C. Case studies-specific assessment of indicators: case study leaders have the possibility to express their opinion on the relevance of the indicators in the light of their specific case study.

Questionnaire

A. General information

In this section some general information is asked. This will help us to interpret your answers in a better way and to follow-up if needed. All data will be treated confidentially.

1. Name and surname
2. Institution you are affiliated with for the MATS project
3. Role in MATS project
 - Partner
 - Advisory group
 - Case study leader
 - Other, please specify:
4. E-Mail

B. General assessment of indicators

This section aims to assess the relevance and quality of the selected indicators in assessing their ability to assess the relationship between trade and sustainability.

To judge the indicators, we would like you to assess their **relevance**: the indicator should help to analyse and measure an important aspect of trade - sustainability relations.

It is also crucial to consider the **quality** of the indicators, those characteristics that make an indicator SMART:

- **Specific:** The measured changes should be expressed in precise terms.
- **Measurable:** Indicators should be related to things that can be measured in an unambiguous way.
- **Achievable:** Indicators should be reasonable and possible to reach and, therefore, sensitive to changes.
- **Replicable:** Measurements should be the same when made by different people using the same method.
- **Time-bound:** There should be a time limit within which changes are expected and measured.

In the following, we ask you to select those indicators that, in your opinion, are most suitable for assessing the relations between trade and sustainability, and that, generally speaking, are relevant and of good quality.

Indicators from the SDG list are codified by three numbers and/or letter that refer to the goal and target to which the indicator belongs; e.g. Indicator 11.4.1 is the first indicators from the fourth target in SDG11.

In your comments please also let us know about your view on the data available at relevant levels and the effort required to obtain data.

POLICY, GOVERNANCE AND REGULATION

This category includes concepts related to international agreements, environmental national policies related to land and energy use, as well as established social and environmental standards, both national and international. Also, concepts related to policy coherence and government spending. In this category also topics related to governance mechanisms, such

as institutional, regulatory, legal and policy frameworks as well as food chain governance and arrangements among private sector actors.

5. Select one or more indicators that you consider RELEVANT and of GOOD quality to accurately help assessing the relation between trade and sustainability in the policy and regulation context.

1.a.2 Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)

1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending

11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)

12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation

15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type

15.4.1 Coverage by protected areas of important sites for mountain biodiversity

2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

6. Please, insert here any comments, doubts, observation that you would like us to consider.
7. Do you have additional indicators to suggest? If applicable, please also specify which organizational benchmark for sustainability indicators you are using, if any / applicable (e.g. GRI, IIED [<https://www.iied.org/monitoring-evaluation-learning>], etc. <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/inofsd.htm>).

HUMAN CAPITAL

This category represents concepts related to individuals that facilitate the creation of personal, social, and economic well-being, the included concepts focus more on poverty rates as well as food & nutrition security, hunger and human rights.

8. Select one or more indicators that you consider RELEVANT and of GOOD quality to accurately help assessing the relation between trade and sustainability in relation to human capital.
 - 1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
 - 1.4.1 Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services
 - 10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
 - 2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
 - 2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
 - 2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height $>+2$ or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)
 - 3.8.1 Coverage of essential health services
 - 3.9.1 Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution
 - 3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)
9. *Please, insert here any comments, doubts, and observation that you would like us to consider.*
10. Do you have additional indicators to suggest? If applicable, please also specify which organizational benchmark for sustainability indicators you are using, if any / applicable (e.g. GRI, IIED [<https://www.iied.org/monitoring-evaluation-learning>], etc. <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/inofsd.htm>).

SOCIAL CAPITAL

This category represents concepts related to society that improve the general livelihood, welfare, and collaboration in the society. This includes labour conditions of citizens, gender equality, social costs, and benefits.

11. Select one or more indicators that you consider to be RELEVANT and of GOOD quality to accurately help assess the relationship between trade and sustainability in relation to social capital.

1.3.1 Proportion of population covered by social protection floors/systems, by sex, distinguishing children, unemployed persons, older persons, persons with disabilities, pregnant women, newborns, work-injury victims and the poor and the vulnerable

10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population

2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status

5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex

5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure

8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex

8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities

8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities

8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

12. *Please, insert here any comments, doubts, and observation that you would like us to consider.*

13. Do you have additional indicators to suggest? If applicable, please also specify which organizational benchmark for sustainability indicators you are using, if any / applicable (e.g. GRI, IIED [<https://www.iied.org/monitoring-evaluation-learning>], etc. <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/inofsd.htm>).

ENVIRONMENT/NATURAL CAPITAL

This category represents the natural asset of resources useful in the agri-food value chain. Both concepts related to the natural inputs have been included like natural input quality or natural sources status; also, concepts more related to the natural capital degradation caused by the chain have been considered like climate impact, footprint, and Emissions.

14. Select one or more indicators that you consider RELEVANT and of GOOD quality to accurately help assessing the relation between trade and sustainability in relation to environment/natural capital.

11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate

12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index

13.2.2 Total greenhouse gas emissions per year

15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area

15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area

15.4.2 Mountain Green Cover Index

6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality

6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources

7.2.1 Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption

8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP

8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

15. *Please, insert here any comments, doubts, observation that you would like us to consider.*

16. Do you have additional indicators to suggest? If applicable, please also specify which organizational benchmark for sustainability indicators you are using, if any / applicable (e.g. GRI, IIED [<https://www.iied.org/monitoring-evaluation-learning>], etc. <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/inofsd.htm>).

KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGY & FACILITIES

This category represents the implementation of sustainable practices, the knowledge transfer and innovation as well as the official assistance and extension for development to actors in the agri-food value chain.

17. Select one or more indicators that you consider RELEVANT and of GOOD quality to accurately help assessing the relation between trade and sustainability in relation to knowledge, technology & facilities.

10.b.1 Total resource flows for development, by recipient and donor countries and type of flow (e.g. official development assistance, foreign direct investment and other flows)

15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management

15.a.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments

17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies

2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture

6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time

6.5.1 Degree of integrated water resources management

6.6.1 Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time

18. *Please, insert here any comments, doubts, observation that you would like us to consider.*

19. Do you have additional indicators to suggest? If applicable, please also specify which organizational benchmark for sustainability indicators you are using, if any / applicable (e.g. GRI, IIED [<https://www.iied.org/monitoring-evaluation-learning>], etc. <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/inofsd.htm>).

ECONOMY AND MARKETS

This category is the one more related directly with trade, it considers regulation of import-export, subsidies, tariff, investments, or any official funds inputs. Also, general aspects of economy have been considered like incomes, production, and economic growth.

20. Select one or more indicators that you consider to be RELEVANT and of GOOD quality to accurately help assess the relation between trade and sustainability in relation to economy & market.

1.a.1 Total official development assistance grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the recipient country's gross national income

10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff

12.c.1 Amount of fossil-fuel subsidies (production and consumption) per unit of GDP

17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports

17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States

2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size

2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector

2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies

2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies

8.1.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita

8.2.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person

8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

21. *Please, insert here any comments, doubts, and observation that you would like us to consider.*

22. Do you have additional indicators to suggest? If applicable, please also specify which organizational benchmark for sustainability indicators you are using, if any / applicable (e.g. GRI, IIED [<https://www.iied.org/monitoring-evaluation-learning>], etc. <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/inofsd.htm>).

C. Case studies specific assessment of indicators

This section is targeted only to those who have a direct relationship with one or more case studies in MATS. We would like to ask you to think about your case study specific context and needs for the planned analysis.

Through the initial and basic information of each case study, we have selected a personalised poll of SDG indicators for each case study. **You can review the list of indicators for your case study on the following link: <https://short.upm.es/bcq83>.**

We would like your thoughts on our initial analysis.

23. Are you representing a case study within the MATS project?

Yes – No

Yes.

24. Which one? _____

25. Do you think our understanding of the case study goes in the right way? Why?

26. Are there indicators that do not match the objective of the case study? Please list them and include a brief explanation.

27. Are there indicators from the general list that you are missing? Please list them and include a brief explanation.

Annex 4: List of SDG indicators selected for each case study

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Case study:

N° 1 – “Effects of trade on commercialization and processing of food products”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category

Economy & Markets

- 1.a.1 Total official development assistance grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the recipient country's gross national income
- 10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
- 17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
- 2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
- 2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
- 8.1.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita
- 8.2.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person
- 8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities

- 2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture

Policy & Regulation

- 1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending

Human Capital

- 1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
- 1.4.1 Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services
- 10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
- 2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
- 2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
- 2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)

Social Capital

- 10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population
- 2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
- 5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
- 8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
- 8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
- 8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Case study:

N° 2 – “Trade, resilience and social sustainability: oats value chain in the Nordics”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category

Economy & Markets

- 2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
- 2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
- 2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
- 2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies
- 8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

Additional indicators that could be useful

17.3.1 Foreign direct investment, official development assistance and South-South cooperation as a proportion of gross national income

Knowledge, Tecnology & Facilities

- 2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture

Policy & Regulation

- 1.a.2 Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)
- 1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending
- 2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

Human Capital

- 1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
- 1.4.1 Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services
- 10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
- 2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
- 2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
- 2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)
- 3.8.1 Coverage of essential health services

Social Capital

- 2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
- 5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
- 5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
- 8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
- 8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
- 8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
- 8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

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Case study:

N° 3 – “Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finish dairy production”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets 10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff 17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports 17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States 2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size 2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector 2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies

Human Capital
3.9.1 Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution 3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities
2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture 6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time 6.5.1 Degree of integrated water resources management 6.6.1 Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time

Environment/Natural Capital
11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate 12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index 13.2.2 Total greenhouse gas emissions per year 15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area 15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area 15.4.2 Mountain Green Cover Index 6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality 6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources 8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP 8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Policy & Regulation
11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal) 12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation 2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

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Case study:

N° 4 – “Accessing export markets with high quality/ social/ environmental standards”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports
17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies
8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements
Additional indicators that could be useful
10.4.2 Redistributive impact of fiscal policy4
17.3.1 Foreign direct investment, official development assistance and South-South cooperation as a proportion of gross national income

Social Capital
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities
15.a.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments
17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies
2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture
Additional indicators that could be useful
12.6.1 Number of companies publishing sustainability reports
7.a.1 International financial flows to developing countries in support of clean energy research and development and renewable energy production, including in hybrid systems

Policy & Regulation
1.a.2 Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)
1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending
11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)
15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type
15.4.1 Coverage by protected areas of important sites for mountain biodiversity
2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

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Case study:

N° 5 – “Role of agricultural inputs and policy regulation in sustainable value chain”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports
17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

Environment/Natural Capital
11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area
15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Policy & Regulation
2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

Human Capital
10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)

Social Capital
10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

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Case study:

N° 6 – “Farm gate process and sustainable business model: towards living income”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

- Overproduction
- Child labor
- Inequality in terms of power
- Risks between producers
- Agriculture expansion and deforestation

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies

Environment/Natural Capital
11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index
15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area
15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities
15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management
17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies
2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture

Social Capital
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities

Additional indicators that could be useful
8.7.1 Proportion and number of children aged 5–17 years engaged in child labour, by sex and age

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Case study:

N° 7 – “Impacts of EU policies on local dairy value chains in Africa”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category	
Economy & Markets	
10.a.1	Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
10.b.1	Total resource flows for development, by recipient and donor countries and type of flow (e.g. official development assistance, foreign direct investment and other flows)
17.11.1	Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports
17.12.1	Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1	Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2	Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
8.1.1	Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita
8.2.1	Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person
8.a.1	Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements
Additional indicators that could be useful	
10.4.2	Redistributive impact of fiscal policy ⁴
17.3.1	Foreign direct investment, official development assistance and South-South cooperation as a proportion of gross national income
Human Capital	
1.1.1	Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
1.4.1	Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services
10.2.1	Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
2.1.2	Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
3.8.1	Coverage of essential health services
Policy & Regulation	
1.a.2	Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)
1.b.1	Pro-poor public social spending
11.4.1	Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)

Environment/Natural Capital	
11.3.1	Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
12.3.1 (a)	Food loss index and (b) food waste index
13.2.2	Total greenhouse gas emissions per year
15.1.1	Forest area as a proportion of total land area
15.3.1	Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
15.4.2	Mountain Green Cover Index
6.3.2	Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality
6.4.2	Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources
8.4.1	Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
8.4.2	Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP
Knowledge, Technology & Facilities	
15.2.1	Progress towards sustainable forest management ¹
15.a.1 (a)	Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments
2.4.1	Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture
6.5.1	Degree of integrated water resources management
Additional indicators that could be useful	
12.6.1	Number of companies publishing sustainability reports
Social Capital	
10.1.1	Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population
2.3.2	Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.1.1	Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
8.3.1	Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1	Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.5.2	Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
8.8.2	Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

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Case study:

N° 8 – “EU climate and energy policies and their influence on trade and land use”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category

Economy & Markets

- 1.a.1 Total official development assistance grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the recipient country's gross national income
- 12.c.1 Amount of fossil-fuel subsidies (production and consumption) per unit of GDP
- 2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
- 2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies

Additional indicators that could be useful

- 7.a.1 International financial flows to developing countries in support of clean energy research and development and renewable energy production, including in hybrid systems

Environment/Natural Capital

- 11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
- 13.2.2 Total greenhouse gas emissions per year
- 15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area
- 15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
- 15.4.2 Mountain Green Cover Index
- 6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality
- 6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources
- 7.2.1 Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption
- 8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
- 8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Additional indicators that could be useful

- 12.a.1 Installed renewable energy-generating capacity in developing countries (in watts per capita)
- 7.1.2 Proportion of population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology

Human Capital

- 2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
- 2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
- 2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)
- 3.9.1 Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution
- 3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)

Additional indicators that could be useful

- 2.2.1 Prevalence of stunting (height for age <-2 standard deviation from the median of the World Health Organization (WHO) Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age

Policy & Regulation

- 1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending
- 11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)

Social Capital

- 10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population
- 5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities

- 17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies

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Case study:

N° 9 – “Human rights and environmental due diligence in the coffee value chain”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
1.a.1 Total official development assistance grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the recipient country's gross national income
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies

Human Capital
1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
1.4.1 Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services
10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)
3.8.1 Coverage of essential health services
3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)
Additional indicators that could be useful
2.2.1 Prevalence of stunting (height for age <-2 standard deviation from the median of the World Health Organization (WHO) Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age

Knowledge, Tecnology & Facilities
2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture
6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time
6.6.1 Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time
Additional indicators that could be useful
12.6.1 Number of companies publishing sustainability reports

Policy & Regulation
1.a.2 Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)
1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending
11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)
12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation

Social Capital
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

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Case study:

N° 10 – “Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
1.a.1 Total official development assistance grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the recipient country's gross national income
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

Environment/Natural Capital
12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index
13.2.2 Total greenhouse gas emissions per year
15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area
15.4.2 Mountain Green Cover Index
6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality
6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources
7.2.1 Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption
8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities
17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies

Human Capital
1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
3.9.1 Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution
3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)

Policy & Regulation
2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

Social Capital
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

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Case study:

N° 11 – “Private standards and sustainable trade”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports
17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies
8.1.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita
8.2.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person
8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements

Social Capital
1.3.1 Proportion of population covered by social protection floors/systems, by sex, distinguishing children, unemployed persons, older persons, persons with disabilities, pregnant women, newborns, work-injury victims and the poor and the vulnerable
10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status
Additional indicators that could be useful
8.7.1 Proportion and number of children aged 5–17 years engaged in child labour, by sex and age

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Case study:

N° 12 – “Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category

Environment/Natural Capital

12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index

Human Capital

1.4.1 Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services
 10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
 2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
 3.8.1 Coverage of essential health services

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities

15.a.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments
 2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture

Policy & Regulation

1.b.1 Pro-poor public social spending

Social Capital

10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population
 2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
 5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
 5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
 8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
 8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
 8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
 8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

Additional indicators that could be useful

8.7.1 Proportion and number of children aged 5–17 years engaged in child labour, by sex and age

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Case study:

N° 13 – “Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
12.c.1 Amount of fossil-fuel subsidies (production and consumption) per unit of GDP
17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
2.c.1 Indicator of food price anomalies
8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements
Additional indicators that could be useful
10.4.2 Redistributive impact of fiscal policy ⁴

Environment/Natural Capital
13.2.2 Total greenhouse gas emissions per year
15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources
8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities
10.b.1 Total resource flows for development, by recipient and donor countries and type of flow (e.g. official development assistance, foreign direct investment and other flows)
17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies

Human Capital
1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)
3.9.1 Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution

Policy & Regulation
12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation
15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type
15.4.1 Coverage by protected areas of important sites for mountain biodiversity
2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures

Social Capital
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

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Case study:

N° 14 – “Changing land-use trajectories due to the EU-Mercosur trade agreement”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
17.11.1 Developing countries and least developed countries' share of global exports
17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies

Knowledge, Technology & Facilities
15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management
17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies
6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time
6.5.1 Degree of integrated water resources management

Environment/Natural Capital
11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area
15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area
15.4.2 Mountain Green Cover Index
6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality
6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources
8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP

Policy & Regulation
11.4.1 Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)
12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation
15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type

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making agricultural trade sustainable

Case study:

N° 15 – “The new generation of EU Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) and their impacts”

1. Words related with SDG Indicators

2. Selected indicators: Divided by category

Indicators by category
Economy & Markets
10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff
17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States
2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size
2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector
2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies
8.1.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita
8.2.1 Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person
8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements
Additional indicators that could be useful
10.4.1 Labour share of GDP
Environment/Natural Capital
11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate
12.3.1 (a) Food loss index and (b) food waste index
6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality
7.2.1 Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption
8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP
Additional indicators that could be useful
7.1.2 Proportion of population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology
Knowledge, Tecnology & Facilities
10.b.1 Total resource flows for development, by recipient and donor countries and type of flow (e.g. official development assistance, foreign direct investment and other flows)
15.a.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments
6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time
Additional indicators that could be useful
14.7.1 Sustainable fisheries as a proportion of GDP in small island developing States, least developed countries and all countries

Human Capital
2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment
2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)
3.9.2 Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene (exposure to unsafe Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for All (WASH) services)
Additional indicators that could be useful
2.2.1 Prevalence of stunting (height for age <-2 standard deviation from the median of the World Health Organization (WHO) Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age
Policy & Regulation
15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type
2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures
Social Capital
2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status
5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex
5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure
8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex
8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities
8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status